

Assessment and Demonstration

Policy Analyses

Two reports within «active interfaces» analyse the framework of energy policy and the effect of prevailing standards and labels on the deployment of building integrated photovoltaic solutions (BIPV). The report "Energy-Policy analysis" [1] gives a short overview on existing policies on cantonal, national and international level. The report "Significance of prevailing regulations, standards and labels for the deployment of BIPV" [2] identifies barriers as well as effects of regulations, standards and labels fostering BIPV-deployment. Barriers and fostering effects are assessed qualitatively with respect to their relevance regarding BIPV deployment.

Key words: Energy policy, standards, labels, effects on deployment of BIPV

Target audience: Regulation makers / Architects & engineers

In the EU as well as in Switzerland we can recognize increasing attention to climate protection and greenhouse gas mitigation targets:

- In Switzerland further development of the model rules for Cantonal energy policy (MuKE) by the conference of the cantonal energy councillors (EnDK) will go towards climate neutral building requirements.
- The new energy concept of the German federal government is also fostering the approach of climate neutral buildings.
- The nearly zero energy approach of the EU-EPBD (Energy Performance for Buildings Directive) also aims towards climate neutral buildings: The requirement that the nearly zero or very low amount of energy required by the building should be covered to a very significant extent by energy from renewable sources, including energy from renewable sources produced on-site or nearby (EPBD Art. 2), delivers almost zero greenhouse gas emissions buildings.

In the building sector this new attention leads to a certain shift of focus from currently prevailing energy conservation and efficiency improvements towards more extensively exploiting existing potentials for renewable energy deployment in order to further decrease greenhouse gas emissions of buildings. This reflects the increase of urgency which is attributed to climate protection. Therefore, the target of climate neutrality of buildings should be prioritised in the future. This will open the range of technical and economical options to further improve buildings towards sustainability, thereby contributing to mitigate the most urgent environmental and resource problems. A future shift of policy priorities towards climate neutrality will foster PV and BIPV deployment.

It is advantageous to base future energy and climate protection policy measures on targets which have to be met and not on particular technical solutions. With regard to BIPV and PV deployment this means that the share of BIPV on overall PV deployment will primarily be a result of the techno-economic viability of BIPV. Within this logic, higher subsidies for BIPV than for PV are not expedient.

In Switzerland the Swiss Energy Strategy 2050 is the framework for the actual and future energy policies. The following figure illustrates this framework and the corresponding laws and planned measures that affect deployment of PV and BIPV. They are discussed in report [1] focussing on issues concerning photovoltaic.

In addition to the mandatory provisions, report [2] also analyses the significance of the most popular Swiss standards and labels on the deployment of PV and BIPV, that is to say the Minergie and the Plusenergy standards.

Mandatory provisions and requirements like the requirement to install PV/BIPV capacities of at least 10 kW_{peak}/m² heated area in new buildings or to have at least 10% renewable energy use in the case of the replacement of a heating system clearly foster deployment of renewable energy, especially of on-site generated PV/BIPV-electricity. Both requirements are defined in the new model rules for cantonal energy policy MuKEN 2014.

Due to costs but also due to energy yields, most of the requirements for on-site renewable energy use or electricity generation facilitate PV deployment which will be first of all PV on the roof or PV integrated in the roof and only afterwards – if these capacities are not sufficient – BIPV in the façades.

BIPV deployment in façades is fostered by the Minergie-A and by the Plusenergy labels. Since the labels and standards are voluntary their impact on BIPV installations will be limited.

References

- [1] Lehmann M., Ott W. (2016). Energy-Policy Analysis. Report 2/3. National Research Programme “Energy Turnaround” (NRP 70) ACTIVE INTERFACES – Holistic strategy to simplify standards, assessments and certification for building integrated photovoltaics. SNF project 153849
- [2] Lehmann M., Ott W. (2017). Significance of prevailing regulations, standards and labels for the deployment of BIPV. Report 3/3. National Research Programme “Energy Turnaround” (NRP 70) ACTIVE INTERFACES – Holistic strategy to simplify standards, assessments and certification for building integrated photovoltaics. SNF project 153849